

Spacetime EPRB Correlations

Bijou M. Smith^{1,*}

¹*AppliedMMT Aotearoa, Wellington, New Zealand*

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There are two known ways around J.S Bell’s famous Inequalities that do not abandon principles of realism and locality. One is to deny Reichenbach’s Common Cause Principle (Bell himself understood this). Another is to impose the lone spin average constraint (Samuel Hedemann discussed this in an obscure preprint). In both cases the Bell Inequality and all generalizations thereof (CHSH, CGLMP and others) cannot be derived, which implies the quantum mechanics correlations one presumes for EPR experiments, and observes, are not necessarily indications of Non-Locality (NL) or anti-Realism (AR). Nevertheless, the orthodox consensus is that our universe is still highly non-classical and EPR-like entanglement correlations are at the heart of the behaviour of non-classical elementary systems. This demands, but we can also say “invites,” a better account of the observed highly non-classical behaviour of entangled systems, which: (1) respects the (very respectable) lone spin average constraint, and (2) mildly disrespects Reichenbach’s principle (RCC), and then (3) explains why one can take the view that either Determinism (D) or (RCC) is violated in quantum processes. We provide a preliminary such account using the principles of topological 4-geon theory (T4G) which leans towards only abandoning the weakest version of (D) possible (deterministic time-evolution) but for very good reason.

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I. INTRODUCTION AND TENSIONS

The Bell-Aspect class of experiments provide convincing evidence for either fundamental non-locality (NL) (if not NL for interactions, then NL for QFT correlators) or measurement-dependent properties (colloquially termed anti-realism (AR)). However, by dropping Reichenbach’s Common Cause Principle (RCC) we cannot derive the Bell Inequalities nor their generalizations nor specializations. This has not perplexed theorists nor experimentalists beyond a few philosophers of physics like Barandes, and maybe J.S. Bell himself [1]. This is for good reason, after all, who would deny RCC?

In probability theory the RCC principle could be regarded as platonic, so neither “quantum” nor “classical,” it is just mathematical logic. But this is not true. It is a rather strong claim, though very reasonable. To deny it is unreasonable and so demands extraordinary justification.

The bite the principle has on physics (so we surmise) is that the typical philosopher thinks physics is not a mere platonic mind game, but is rather mechanical¹ and quasi-deterministic and “weird but not too weird.” These are

¹ Does anyone ever wonder why quantum physics is still called *mechanics*? Is mere ‘time-evolution’ a sufficient behaviour to be conceived of as ‘mechanical’?

* achrononmaster@gmail.com

terms we guess are at the heart of most psychological prejudices that support the RCC.

Ironically, by dropping RCC we might gain a more mechanistic understanding of quantum physics, and that is what the present paper seeks to discuss. We try to land on *not* needing to abandon RCC while retaining local realism and causality. But, there’s always a “but”! The theorist still must abandon some classical mechanics, and so the question becomes what exactly must be abandoned if the EPR experiments have no force on our commitments to NL or AR?

In §II we review some implications of dropping RCC, and discuss whether *both* Locality (L) and Realism (R) can be recovered. Throughout this paper we restrict consideration to probabilities that arise in physics. This may raise the question, “What do you mean by *physics*?” which is far too metaphysical a topic, and so what we will mean is quantum theory as we broadly understand it today, including all the various wild interpretations and frameworks. Although incestuous (defining a field of study by only its models is probably not a great idea) we leave it up to readers to impose their own favourite definition of *Physics* upon our discussion as their alternative lens, but ask them to indulge ours for the time being.

Some Caveats: this paper has no claim to originality, we are just repackaging extant literature. We have also laboured to keep the exposition as simple as possible but no simpler. Others more capable can surely ‘go to town’ on turning some of our claims into mathematical conjectures and proofs. However, in this combinatorial exercise in literature repackaging we believe an opportunity of a change in perspective on QM and QFT is afforded, and that can be viewed as some kind of original breakthrough— for the reader, not for ourselves.

We will explore Hedemann’s turn (enforcing lone spin averages= 0) too in §III, but not in detail.

In §IV we develop the main concept of this paper, which is the topological 4-geon theory view of entanglement, and how we can retain our most cherished principles. A vindication of Einstein’s point of view.

A few more philosophical remarks are indulged in subsections IV.G to IV.J before the partly sociological commentary summary.

I.A. Comments on Other Resolutions

Others have favoured retaining (L) and (R) and taking something called ‘superdeterminism’ (SD)² as a metaphysical primary (the future is just set-in-stone and has the EPR correlations baked-in). We will not entertain this position, mainly because in our view it is without meaning in a 4D Block Universe — which is the setting

² A simple colloquial characterization of (SD) is *denial of freedom of choice of settings*.

for our preferred framework of topological 4-geon theory. However, one comment on this is that in a 4D Block Universe things *are* “baked-in” but the structure of the spacetime cobordism should be³ scientifically comprehensible, and so-called superdeterminism seems ad hoc and so incomprehensible. The baking of the spacetime pie, in other words, in T4G theory, is something we aim to show is more elegant and — for want of a better word — tastier.⁴

Huw Price [2] and others provide alternatives too, as do those who hold to the Transactional Interpretation [3]. In Price’s case, the resolution is to admit backwards causation. Much like superdeterminism, we find this unpalatable and in any case also a bit meaningless in a 4D Block Universe, where again the more interesting scientific question is why the dickens would the spacetime cobordism admit backwards causation? (Or what Feynman termed somewhat confusingly “advanced causation” — meaning the cause was ahead in time of the effect.)

On the Transactional Interpretation one could regard it as akin to Price’s backwards causal signal propagation. There are differences in these views, but we have the same objection, since once again, why would the universe have these forwards and backwards handshakes? To be more precise, why is the Transactional handshake the fundamental ‘mechanism’? And why not ask, is there a simpler explanation for the same overall effect?

Why, furthermore, do these signalings *only* occur in the ‘spooky’ way for Bell pairs and the like? What the Laplace devil is that all about?

The same overall effect is that described well by Yakir Aharonov, in the Two-Time view of quantum mechanics [4]. This is the view that for some unknown reason all experiments (that are sensitive to entanglement and superposition) must specify two times (at least) and we may only employ our model of reality to these boundaries. Once again, we would ask the same naïve questions — why is *this* level of description your bedrock? Is there not something far simpler underpinning all these non-classical interpretations of what we all know is certainly a non-classical physics of our cosmos?

Not wishing to be exhaustive in review here, one other point of view worth mentioning is that our universe is a cellular automata of some sort, a mere computation. At least one person in the world regards this as a moral abomination, but even if we do not care for their kind, there is an intellectual hazard in computationalism, which is that since all of experimental physics can be numerically simulated — because *we choose to define physics by things we can mathematize!* — there is an obviously glaring enormous confirmation bias at play, which

³ Unapologetically so, a moral commitment to the enterprise commonly regarded as ‘Science’, at least by retrograde oldies like one chap by the name of A. Einstein, who morally wanted the universe to be comprehensible.

⁴ Some would say “more beautiful” but Pie is not all that flash.

we find utterly hilarious the computationalists seem to be oblivious towards, almost intellectually blinded.

Somewhat related are Emergentists, who seek to emerge spacetime physics from some other substrate. But all we do in physics occurs in spacetime, so at some point in the future of science these theories will demand peeling away the supposed façade of spacetime. The spacetime realist position (our position) — which presumes there is no façade — is distinct from the aforementioned confirmation bias. Since, **(a)** it is possible to experimentally show spacetime is not real if it is not real. (By contrast one can never prove computationalism is false with computation, with computation one can only disqualify particular models, which is very weak tea indeed, as the Englishmen might say.) And **(b)** Spacetime realism is an almighty constraint, there is little to no wiggle-room for models that take 4D spacetime as fundamental. (Postulating Calabi–Yau dimensions is not our cup of tea — way too strong.)

Nevertheless, it is possible spacetime doomerism will win out in the end, but reports of the death of spacetime have, to our knowledge, been subject to the Mark Twain glitch.

Having noted that, let’s finish up this philosophical vein by noting that there is more to the *Meaning of Lif* than four coordinates and the consequences thereof. Even if spacetime realism stands the test of time, we, for a few at least, are pretty convinced there is more. Our view would be not that “spacetime is doomed,” but the worldview that *only spacetime exists* has to be laughably naïve and ridiculous. What implications that has for proper *Physics* though is anyone’s guess, and we have nothing to say about that worth reading without triggering too many intellectuals.

II. POSSIBLE IMPLICATIONS OF DROPPING RCC

The denials of RCC or statistical independence (SI) are important because they are not EPRB experiment loopholes. The experiments prove beyond a shadow of doubt that the entangled pair correlations are highly non-classical. But the loopholes they cover are Locality and Causality. The experiments cannot cover Non-Local HV’s, (RCC) and (SI), at least not as the experiments are presently engineered.

Proposing that either (SI) or (RCC) do not hold for physical reality is already non-classical. Classical mechanics, for example, is not superdeterministic (SD) — meaning there is no way to account for the EPR correlations in classical mechanics without trivializing time evolution as a baked-in conspiracy of sorts. Although ‘conspiracy’ is the wrong word, being too heavily emotionally overloaded, it yet seems to be in common parlance when discussing superdeterminism.

Palmer [5] has a model that defends (SD) as “non-conspiratorial” but only at the cost of some severe pre-

sumptions (like a finite Hilbert space). We cannot say his model is wrong, but would prefer to not comment upon it, because we believe we have a better explanation for EPR correlations.

In superdeterminism resolutions, like ‘t Hooft’s sketchy cellular automata physics modelling [6], the EPR correlations are somehow baked-in to the universe. That may be the case, but the EPRB generation of experiments are not tests for such models. Thus we have very flimsy empirical support either way for or against the (SD) variety of denial of (SI).

In [7] Barandes points out that,

“Bell’s principle of local causality . . . implicitly depends on an assumption that goes beyond questions of locality. That implicit assumption is called Reichenbach’s principle of common causes.”

There is potentially a sociology of physics issue here in that (we agree) it *goes beyond questions of locality*. As alluded to in the introduction, we suspect some psychology enters the physics literature here, because — very reasonably — physicists worry about locality and realism, and not all of us have sought the false shelter of Idealism yet. We are still in the proverbial bunkers fighting the war against excessive subjectivity. The theory of probability, or more to the point, the philosophy of the theory of probability was horribly muddled for physicists at the early stages of the development of quantum physics, so much so that in the context of quantum theory physicists have almost lost a grip on what probability means.

Our view is that probability is a mathematical concept, and has firm pragmatic foundations, despite what modernizers like Misha Gromov [8] insist we should worry about. The nuances of Gromov may be important, but we do not think they implicate quantum physics any more than general physics.

Another reason (RCC) is interesting is that it can take the theorizing beyond questions of locality. Again partly because the experiments are probing Locality and Weak Causality (special relativity (SR)) but not (RCC).

Barandes [9] also has a partial resolution of the issue, which is that it is in fact possible to reformulate all of quantum theory (including QFT) without talking about mysterious “*probability amplitudes*.” We would go further and read Barandes as saying the whole notion of a ‘probability amplitude’ is a huge misnomer. His framework of Indivisible Stochastic QM (ISQM) reproduces all of orthodox QM with no mention of the amplitudes. Instead, he has unistochastic matrix elements, which are in his framework clearly not *probabilities*. They are entries in a non-Markov transition matrix. Generically many entries will be negative numbers. The strictly positive non-Markov transition matrix squares the unistochastic entries,

$$\Gamma_{ij}(t) = |U_{ij}|^2$$

the crucial bit of physics is that while the unitary numbers U_{ij} which (more or less) are the solutions to the

Schrödinger or Dirac equations of motion (for an elementary system) satisfy smooth divisible transitions,

$$U(t) = U(t \leftarrow t_0)U(t_0) \quad (\text{Divisible})$$

while the physical transition matrix does not, in general,

$$\Gamma(t) \neq \Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma(t_0) \quad (\text{Indivisible}).$$

In a pattern which should be thoroughly familiar to gauge theory practitioners and general relativists, the failure of Γ to be divisible is identifiable as the interference terms in Schrödinger or Dirac time evolution. The common pattern is that departures from a trivial composition law encode physical structure: curvature appears when covariant derivatives fail to commute; gauge fields appear when gauge-covariant derivatives fail to commute; and quantum correlations appear when transition amplitudes fail to factorize.

Without an ontology explaining why, Barandes goes on to show explicitly that Reichenbach’s common cause principle (RCC) fails in the case of indivisible stochastic dynamics (see §-IV of [9]). This means the Bell Inequalities cannot be derived for any quantum theory that is consistent with ISQM.

To recover the Bell Inequalities would therefore seem to require new postulates of quantum physics, which would be *inconsistent* with the current orthodox foundations. If this seems shocking, it is equally shocking Barandes’ work has not been very shocking to the physics community. It is *as if* most physicists still do not really care much about foundations.

II.A. Disproving RCC is Hard

First we should note that for many of the non-fundamental sciences Reichenbach’s Principle is clearly false. For example, if you tabulate coin flips and only count those where at least one of them is heads. You hand the table to a friend and note whenever coin A flipped tails coin B was sure to be heads. RCC implies there is a common cause in the coins flip outcomes, which is clearly false. The error is due to failure to consider the *statisticians collider* process Fig. 1,

FIG. 1: The collider is a common effect, and induces a correlation between A and B that does not satisfy Reichenbach’s Principle.

However, for fundamental processes RCC is hard to dislodge, and is not easily proven to be false. It is a good principle, and not a light thing to abandon. In the case

of the coin flip table the tabulation is obviously not a record of fundamental processes, so RCC is not falsified thereby, it is just *not applicable*.

As failure of RCC it could then be the case that entanglement processes, or at least EPRB measurements, are not exactly fundamental. This is true, the whole effect of gathering the correlations is fairly complicated and not fundamental at all, even if entanglement is a fundamental state of two qubits.

As a counterpoint, perhaps new postulates for QM and QFT are needed! In an analysis of extensions of probability spaces with respect to fixed measures, Hofer-Szabó et al [10] argue that

“... the behavior of correlations with respect to Bell’s inequality is not a good indicator of (non)existence of *common* common causes.”

A concept [10] introduces is *completeability of common cause*. It is worth quoting them at length to avoid a naïve misreading:

“There exist both classical and quantum probability spaces that contain correlations without containing proper common causes of the correlations; hence, if one wants to maintain Reichenbach’s Common Cause Principle, one must be able to claim that there might exist ‘hidden’ events (‘hidden’ in the sense of not being accounted for in the common cause incomplete event structure) that can be interpreted as the common causes of the correlations. If such ‘hidden’ common cause events exist, then there must exist an extension of the original probability space, an extension that accommodates the common causes. Propositions 2 and 3 [*in their paper*] tell us that such extensions are always possible. In other words, [*their*] Propositions 2 and 3 show that a necessary condition for a common cause explanation of correlations in both classical and quantum event structures can always be satisfied. To put this negatively: one cannot disprove Reichenbach’s Common Cause Principle by proving that the necessary condition (common cause completeability) for its validity cannot be satisfied.”

It should become evident later that we take this as half of an argument that quantum mechanics is incomplete⁵, rather than a refutation of (RCC). But for now the spotlight is on RCC.

There is, we think, a very perspicuous remark made by Hofer-Szabó et al., which touches upon our later contribution to this discussion from T4G theory. They write [10, Sec.6],

⁵ Incomplete *but in an interesting way*. To wit, “There is no wavefunction Neo, but anyway, incompleteness was not the wavefunction’s fault.”

“Whether or not common cause closed probability spaces exist, it is not reasonable to expect a probabilistic physical theory to be common cause closed. This is because one does not expect to have a proper common cause explanation of probabilistic correlations that arise as a consequence of a direct physical influence between the correlated events, or which are due to some logical relations between the correlated events. One would want to have a common cause explanation of correlations between events that are neither directly causally related, nor do they stand in straightforward logical consequence relations to each other.”

We beg the readers indulgence to let that quote hang in the mind space for a while before we revisit this same point in §IV.H. A teaser is that this seems to argue for a reasonable relaxation (of some unspecified nature) to (RCC). But could you foresee how to relax (RCC) without foregoing (RCC)? Perhaps in physics probability analysis should pay careful attention to statements made about time-ordering of events, would you not agree?

* * *

In another view of common cause principles, Rédei [11] finds that it remains an open question whether or not the event structure defined by (algebraic) quantum field theory is common cause incomplete. What Rédei does show is a conditional: *if* all superluminal correlations predicted by the vacuum state between events in the observable algebras \mathcal{A} of spacelike separated regions V_1, V_2 *do* have a genuine probabilistic common cause, *then* the local algebras $\mathcal{A}(V_1)$ and $\mathcal{A}(V_2)$ must be statistically independent “in the sense of C^* -independence.”

This motivates a compulsion for theorists to hold-on to RCC in order to keep statistical independence (SI). We could include (SI) in the menu of cherished notions we do not wish too readily to abandon in physics model building.

To square this with Barandes we would have to say that ISQM (and by backwards implication orthodox QM) admits *there might be* hidden variables. This is hardly world news. Also at stake is some variety of determinism (D), add that to the menu. This could mean that Hamiltonian time evolution is abandoned (so also it would deny the Many Worlds view).

Our T4G theory is sympathetic to this point of view, we will show why later in §IV.

The interesting thing is that we seem to be rewarded with now five or six cherished principles we would not like to abandon too hastily, statistical independence (SI), Locality (L), Realism (R), Determinism (D), Local Causality (LC), and now Common Cause (RCC), or common cause completeability.

We are aware those who think deeply about such things might find these are not an independent set, though we

cannot comment one way or the other without an unnecessary digression.

Suppose we do keep RCC, then a good review of what the remaining options are for branching our QM model building is the article by Howard Wiseman [12]. Wiseman does not seem to discuss (SI) separate to a notion of Locality (aka. parameter independence) and/or Jarrett-completeness (aka. outcome independence), and focuses mostly on Locality and Relativistic Causality which is close enough to (LC).

Wiseman also draws the branch point for model options fairly well, using a bifurcation split into two camps: Realists and Operationalists:

“For realists, the notion of local causality, ruled out by Bell’s 1976 theorem, is motivated implicitly by Reichenbach’s Principle of common cause and explicitly by the Principle of relativistic causality, and it is the latter which must be forgone. Operationalists pay no heed to Reichenbach’s Principle, but wish to keep the Principle of relativistic causality, which, bolstered by an implicit ‘Principle of agent-causation’, implies their notion of locality. Thus for operationalists, Bell’s theorem is the 1964 one, and implies that it is determinism that must be forgone.”

This seems to us a gross partition, because other Camps could exist, those who abandon (SI) or (RCC) — that is “pay heed to” but abandon RCC and keep (LC). As well as the fringe Camp who seek to avoid abandoning any of the above, and instead modifying Quantum Theory itself.

Without a better foundation for quantum theory the philosopher can argue for abandoning any one of them and yet happily *only* one of them. Not so much a Sophie’s Choice any more?

Well, you put more food on the table and the appetite just expands to meet the optical space. Meaning that it really does not matter how many options we have, because absent hard experimental data showing us precisely which principle to abandon we are no better off. One may only psychologically think the situation is healthier. But one cherished principle flown away is going to be bitter loss to some sector of the physics community. We would still rather keep all the aforementioned principles. It is not greed, it is model hygiene (for want of a better word), perhaps we should say the universe is more comprehensible if we can find a way to retain all the principles. Comprehensibility is good to have in science.

II.B. Modifying RCC

Cavalcanti et al [13] take another approach, by pointing out “modified forms of Reichenbach’s principle could be maintained even with relativistic causality.”

Their approach is to break down (RCC) into two pieces, (i) common cause proper (CCP), and (ii) factorization of probabilities (FP). Our buffet menu expanded again.

They achieve a negative result: one way to retain a modification of (RCC) is so-called ‘*non-commutative common cause*’ which they show fails to explain EPR correlations.

They also report on a result (see [14]) we had not read before, which is that,

“Recently it has been shown [*in [14]*] that any causal theory for the Bell correlations that maintains the RCC must feature such a ‘fine-tuning’ of the causal parameters in the theory, that is, any such causal model must ‘hide’ some causal channels available at the underlying level from use by macroscopic agents in the world.”

This road led to looking at Leifer and Spekkens’ model of *quantum theory as Bayesian belief propagation* [15]. It is hard to know how to characterize this approach, but like Barandes’ ISQM, it is a class of stochastic interpretation of quantum mechanics, so in the present author’s view it does not address realist ontology clearly enough to be worth expounding upon. So-called *quantum Bayesianism* is a lot like a cousin to computationalism — it is hard to impossible to falsify, so falls under metaphysical umbrella status, not hard concrete physics. The ontological commitments, if any, appear too baroque for the purposes of this present paper, where we are adopting a more radical minimalism and looking for 4D spacetime physics solutions. That is, physical ontology that explains the probabilities and EPR correlations, not a theory where probability is primitive or irreducible or fundamental and any of those sorts of adjectives.

Undoubtedly, if a modification of (RCC) can be found consistent with quantum correlations then it would provide a good starting point. We think that is provided by Barandes’ ISQM framework. Though as we will see shortly, we take a different view of post-ISQM theory to Barandes himself.

II.C. The Bullet Bitten by Barandes

In some talks Jacob Barandes seems to flirt with dropping (RCC), but in this paper [7] a different tack is taken. The very notion of *casual* is redefined [7, sec.IV]; a *unistochastic system* is taken to be composed of two subsystems Q , and R .

“A theory with microphysical directed conditional probabilities is causally local if any pair of localized systems Q and R that remain at spacelike separation for the duration of a given physical process do not exert causal influences on each other during that process, in

the sense that the directed conditional probabilities for Q are independent of R , and vice versa.”

The upshot is that Barandes can have a LHV theory. The HV’s are a bit vague, but can probably be regarded as “the laws of the unistochastic process.” So a merological HV?

The bullet bitten is (D) — but in a severe way, because it is dropping even metaphysical Determinism, because what is causal (via laws) is really all there is to Physics. However, this is unlikely to cause a stir amongst physicists because by now generations of physicists have been bred and raised with an immunity to mental health ill effects of indeterminism. Who is to say whether that is good or bad?

In other seminars Barandes has explained the view he elicits from ISQM is a local hidden variables view (LHV), but deeply hidden, meaning unobservable, which we read as the same as dropping (D).

We will return to this question later (page 11, and will consider that although physicists should not be content with stopping at stochastic laws as the final words science has to offer, we can still sacrifice elements of determinism (D) without relenting to stochastic laws as primary.

This is still interesting and provocative, and we do have a T4G theory view of this bullet, although to appreciate this fully we would recommend reading through our §IV. We will find that T4G theory has a subscription to the 4D Block Universe, or at least Ellis’ Crystallizing BU. Overall spacetime Determinism is then a moot point, and T4G lands in the rather, shall we say, Zen-like metaphysics camp of All Things are Determined by Something. However, that is not T4G physics, it is just philosophy. Maybe, like John A. Wheeler, one could say some puppet masters in the future are twiddling our strings? It is not a worthy physics question if we have no way to tell one way or the other except moral indignation (which we do possess).

The other stance we can take is that *for all practical purposes* T4GT gives us indeterminism. But unlike Barandes retains metaphysical Determinism if you want it. We can dodge bullets.

* * *

Later we want to look at Samuel Hedemann’s refutation of the very *Inequalities* of J.S. Bell, where we will briefly mention the Scott Aaronson sanity test: can you program two *classical* computers, Alicebot and Bobbot and fly them apart and get EPRB correlations out of querying them?

How does Barandes’ account of EPR fare? Would the Shtetl Optimized bury Jacob in a pile of blogging dirt? I don’t think so, because no matter how we slice it, you cannot get Barandes’ ISQM from a classical theory, if you can bite on the (D) bullet and chew it up, then I think the way it goes is that Alicebot and Bobbot have some sort of indivisibility resource, and so when queried will

spit out the EPRB correlations, because that’s just what The Laws say they should do. All the programmer has to do is write some sort of indivisible stochastic transition matrix program, but you cannot do this on a classical computer, you’d need a quantum computer. Barandes is safe from getting Shetl’ed. Gets to keep hold of LHV.

We find this a lot like David Chalmers’ wacky concept of consciousness as arising from an actual Bridging Law between the physical/objective and the mental/subjective. “Why?” one asks, and the reply is, “It just *is!*”

III. THE LONE SPIN AVERAGE ESCAPE ROUTE

This is a perplexing case, and there is scant discussion in the literature, and so we would only like to draw attention to the work and leave adjudication to others.

Hedemann [16] constructs a Non-Local HV model (which is perfectly admissible) but claims it can be construed as a Local HV (LHV), which, unless he drops (RCC) should be impossible, and yet he does not forego (RCC).

The escape route he takes is to increase correlations between our familiar EPRB set-up, A and B , by adding constraints. This is perfectly fine, and to be expected. However, his analysis permits one degree of freedom, which is to insert the EPR correlation $-\cos(\theta_{ab})$ into the system of equations he solves. This system is the full set of constraints on the traditional EPRB experiment.

The simplicity almost seems deceptive. What J.S. Bell does not do is enforce lone spin average constraints:

$$\langle \sigma_a \rangle = 0 = \langle \sigma_b \rangle$$

Those constraints are perhaps implicit in Bell’s papers, or surely have not been entirely over-looked, but perhaps they were? We cannot judge having come to most of the EPRB literature cold, or lukewarm. But have you ever heard lone spin averages talked about at EPR conferences?

It is at least true that non-trivial constraints (or constraints independent of others) do tend to raise correlations, so why not raise them above the classical correlation function?

The answer is you need to have a model that increases the correlations. The classical spins, or helicities, will still not suffice. Why then can Hedemann justify plugging in the $E(A, B) = -\cos(\theta_{ab})$ quantum correlation function as one of his constraints? He is presuming what he wants to prove?

It seemed this way to us upon first reading, but we think Hedemann is a bit more subtle. All he is saying is that none of the EPRB *experiments* have ruled out LHV’s.

This should give one some pause, because the blistering attacks in the physics community get deployed whenever anyone attempts to show J.S. Bell’s Inequalities are

invalid. But note, Hedemann is not claiming the quantum correlations are wrong. Nature still violates the Bell Inequalities. All Hedemann is saying, at first, is that we cannot derive the Bell Inequalities in the first place. There are too many constraints in the system to loosen the correlations below the EPR correlation.

If Hedemann’s analysis stands, then it is still a bit shocking no one noticed this before (perhaps some have?) What then have all the EPRB–Aspect–Clauser–Zeilinger experiments been proving?

The answer is they were proving the world is very non-classical when entanglement occurs. But none of the cherished Principles need to be abandoned.

Hedemann takes this as bait. Could he then discover a model that reproduces the EPR correlation with (non-classical) Local HV’s?

Now this is where we depart from Hedemann. Hedemann conjures up an electrodynamics model that has, what he calls, a two-type absorption. The EPR correlations are then accounted for with an oscillator mechanism, which keeps the two spacelike separated systems correlated, since undisturbed they have this same internal clock. At this point his electrodynamics absorption mechanism ceases to be relevant (it is just an explicit exemplar now), because what he really needs is that our Alice and Bob make their spin measurements exactly at the same time, so the oscillators are at the same phase — relative to their state at the source. (Presumably we need the Labs to be inertial? We’re not sure about a relativistic set-up.) The crucial thing is the near simultaneity of the measurements.

Hedemann says, in effect, the EPR correlations are therefore really an artefact of *all the experiments ever done* requiring coincidence counters. The correlations, he might say, are forced by the experimentalist when they use only the statistics from coincidence counters.

We think that’s good news, since that makes Hedemann’s model falsifiable, so in the end he is not truly sticking in the EPR correlation by hand in his system of constraints. He’s just saying, we should use those constraints, and so not use the Bell Inequality as the test of all the cherished Principles!

Thus, if Hedemann is correct, then this should still be big news, and the Nobel Prizes for EPRB stuff should be edited slightly. They were showing we do not live in a classical world. Phew! That’d be horrific, right? Nobel Prize justified.

But local realism, or local causality, or LHV’s are still in play for models of our physical reality. You could say the suspicions of Einstein and his pals are not dead yet.

For the nerds who follow such things, we might mention Hedemann should not cause Scott Aaronson any ire, because if you put Hedemann’s model on a pair of computers and fling them apart at light speed then Scott can easily set-up EPR correlations if he knows the detections will be filtering out all but coincidence counts. No cheating Charlie third intermediating computer is needed. However, Bertlmann’s socks would need some-

thing jiggling inside them.

III.A. Interim Assessment

Given all the above considerations, it might seem now less of an Houdini Act to escape annihilation of five of the six cherished principles. Most readers may think it would still be a magic show illusion to escape all annihilation whatsoever. However, one should not be too pessimistic, because the intellectual wiggle room generated by reviewing the literature (and we have not touched more than a tiny fraction of it) might be cause for hope for finding a safe haven for all of the aforementioned principles.

IV. A T4G POINT OF VIEW

In a preprint [17] we have outlined T4G theory (topological 4-geon theory) and compared with Barandes’ Indivisible Stochastic QM [9]. Partly because T4G is a largely unrecognized framework we will provide a review, but will keep it fairly brief and non-technical, though hopefully this will also encourage researchers to look at variations on the same theme.

IV.A. Cobordism Boundaries and Logic of QM

Topological 4-geon theory began with the work of Mark Hadley in the mid-1990’s, [18]. This is a non-classical extension of General Relativity made by permitting closed timelike curves at the Planck scale. It is not a theory that allows time-travel *per se*, since not much need be presumed capable of traversing the CTC’s. One can generalize T4G into a non-spacetime theory too, by supposing the CTC’s are merological, or any other ontology, but for our purposes we would prefer it if others pursuing such directions use a different nomenclature, and we wish to reserve ‘T4G’ for the 4D spacetime version of the more generic framework.

The focus of T4G theory is the two boundaries of a given spacetime cobordism region, which we define as any two 3D boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 of relevance in a one-shot experiment. The two times t_1 to t_2 define the experiment interval. (Restricting to one-shot is just a convenience, since compositionality of these partial or T4G-cobordisms applies.⁶)

T4G-cobordisms naturally compose, and form a category, however they do not factorize in the ISQM sense, meaning they are *indivisible* — the stochastic transitions describing a T4G-cobordism will not compose — when

FIG. 2: T4G-cobordisms can be indivisible. Note: though this looks like a Coleman baby universe, that’s the wrong impression, this wormhole feature could be some more exotic structure, we’ve just illustrated a generic sort of topology.

there is entanglement. Composition-wise this means nothing but the fact if we surgically remove all the wormholes then we lose information (Figure 2), and as we shall shortly see in §IV.B, we’d lose some EPR correlations.

In T4G theory however, the indivisibility is more than statistical, because we are using Hadley’s framework [19], where the future boundary ∂M_2 may provide non-redundant data. Moreover, the data on ∂M_2 can seem arbitrary, since a boundary ∂M_3 (with $t_3 > t_2$) may have ER-bridges to ∂M_2 . This implies in T4G theory the *monotonic time evolution* story is irreducibly stochastic and non-deterministic.

A T4G-cobordism differs from a spacetime algebra cobordism (ST-cobordism) in admitting closed timelike curves, which make the *quantum channel* [20] “leaky”. However, T4G theory does not require actual CTC traversals, only the near possibility. Just plain vanilla ER-bridges, Minkowski-nonlocal connections between spacelike separated regions are sufficient to define a quantum theory in the T4G framework.

The only time-travel paradoxes are the banal ones where qubits do undergo a nearly CTC path, but they already knew they would (were they conscious!). Such kinematics consistent with extension of GR were described by Navikov, Echeverria and others [21, 22].

When the quantum channel does not factorize then we *conjecture* that this is functorially equivalent to the T4G-cobordism containing wormholes or some (perhaps more exotic) type of CTC structure, and equivalent (up to functorial correspondence) to the ISQM indivisible stochastic maps. To be clear, *CTC structure* does not imply particles will traverse CTC paths, but any particle might traverse a nearly CTC path, or in the process undergo the Stückelberg transform.

In short: T4G is already a quantum theory [18]. While that reference can be consulted, we would like to provide a self-contained synopsis for the present reader. There can be an elementary proof of a weak theorem (we will have to just say it is a ‘Result’) that T4G theory is a quantum theory.

Hadley [18] showed that provided CTCs can provide non-redundant Cauchy data then the generic T4G cobordism has the measurement proposition logic of quan-

⁶ A T4G-cobordism is a variety of partial spacetime cobordism. However, while T4G-cobordisms compose, they do not factorize, meaning in the ISQM sense to be explained.

tum mechanics. However, if elementary particles and spacetime vacuum contain ubiquitous wormhole structure, then the generic T4G-cobordism will induce a quantum theory on the boundaries. To complete the proof we would at this point in history need to add the postulate that the vacuum does contain CTC structure, or the elementary particles contain wormhole-like structure, since there is no known proof nor empirical evidence yet for this necessary condition in the theorem.

However, there is another way to prove the same theorem, which is to establish a functorial equivalence between aspects of T4G-cobordism boundary maps and ISQM, this was outlined in [17].

In T4G then, we are — in agreement with Barandes [9] — not altering what we regard by the words “*probability theory*.” In this lens on QM, probability is still Kolmogorov, but we admit the t -parameterized spacetime cobordism generically is non-Markovian⁷, and in particular indivisible, again exactly as per Barandes.

* * *

When above we stated, “One can generalize T4G into a non-spacetime theory too, by supposing the CTC’s are merological, or any other ontology” — there is a further point to that remark, which is that tension with experiments that probe detailed decoherence, Tsirelson bounds, cluster decomposition and even wormhole-like EPR structure itself, could potentially invalidate a minimalist 4D spacetime picture.

At minimum what T4G needs to more rigorously demonstrate (theoretically at least) is geometrodynamics that includes,

- The Stueckelberg mechanism — for in pure spacetime with Lorentzian causal structure there is simply no other way to explain anti-particles without adding extra metaphysical fields. T4G eschews field theory for obvious reasons of parsimony (though we are not claiming field theory is wrong, we merely wish to see what can be done with a picture where the fields are fictional accounting tools).
- EPR effects — the focus of this present paper.
- Interference — also meaning superposition of “the right amount.” This is a possibly new coin of phrase in the literature because what on earth could we mean by “some amount of” superposition?
- Reasonable Tsirelson bounds.

- The Minimal LR-symmetric Standard Model algebra — the full graded algebra being more the focus in spacetime physics than the mere symmetries. This we do have [24].

There are probably many other issues to work on, we will refrain from attempting an exhaustive list.

Comment on superposition: the idea in T4G theory is roughly the same as Barandes’ ISQM, which is that superposition “is not real” but is rather an *effective* account of indivisible stochastic dynamics. At the statistical level of explanation we believe there is no difference here between T4GT and ISQM. Interference is of course very real. No cause for alarms bells though, since in the field theory description we cannot do without complete superposition. This is because, as remarked above, in a given finite time interval T4G-cobordism region we never have complete information, so have no way to constrain the amount of modelled superposition the field theory needs to presume.

This is fine, since, according to T4GT and ISQM, quantum mechanics is a stochastic transition theory of boundary data, not a theory of anything that actually takes place in the interior of the spacetime cobordism envelope of interest (the “experiment”). Thus the superpositions can totally be regarded as fictional, as mere accounting tools. QM is silent on the interior, and T4GT is a theory that suggests why QM must be silent, and even why any theory we can effectively work with must also be silent about the cobordism interior.

Comment on Tsirelson bounds: because a fully developed T4GT *would be* a fully fledged quantum gravity theory, it should by rights explain decoherence and “emergence” of the classical limit. In other words, a deep explanation for the Correspondence Principle. The method by which this would work in T4G theory is a form of gravitational decoherence, but differs fairly dramatically from the Penrose–Diósi mechanism, and is closer to the type of decoherence discussed by Joseph Samuel [25].

On the Penrose–Diósi theory, which claims “quantum superpositions of states involving a significant mass displacement should have a finite lifetime . . .” — T4G would differ because there are no actual superpositions of spacetime in the T4G picture. However, we would say that the statistical effectiveness of the T4G superpositions surely does imply finite lifetimes for those statistical effects. This is because, as in the GPT (Generalized Probability Theory framework, see [26]) in T4G theory superposition and entanglement are inseparable aspects of any quantum theory. If one considers only the data on the T4G-cobordism boundaries ∂M_1 to ∂M_2 and gives up knowing what all the equivalent quantum channel leakages and injections are which impart memory effects, then the T4G theory restricted to these boundaries is a quantum theory: the state transitions are continuous and reversible, which is the key quantum GPT distinction between classical mechanics and quantum mechanics [27] (in CM the state transitions are reversible but not continuous — we do not get transitions in-between a landed dice throw

⁷ Hence has memory effects. We have not made any connection to the memory effects in the Pasterski–Strominger infrared triangle relations [23].

showing \square , and \square , et cetera).

We should add, the states in QM are also fictional accounting tools, because they are field variables even in NRQM, and the QFT really makes no difference from the T4G point of view. The field variables are as Feynman argued [28] and as Barandes' ISQM also claims, fictional accounting tools to generate smooth Hamiltonian time evolution — *in our models*, not necessarily in physical reality. In the proper spacetime Lagrangian formalism these field variables are not needed, one only needs the advanced and retarded particle trajectories, the reason everyone adopts field theory is a convenience, albeit practically necessary. Apart from maybe the Amplituhedron program [29, 30] it seems impossible to dispense with these accounting tools. What T4G offers is not an alternative calculational set of tools, but merely a new way to comprehend *why* this near practical necessity is forced upon us.

To be blunt about it, if you had a time travelling Doctor Who messing up your laboratory experiments like a little leprechaun, you too would be forced to use field theory, and hope that The Doctor is at least keeping to the local symmetry rules.

IV.B. EPR from T4G

We turn now to the main focus of this paper, which is to show fairly explicitly how T4G explains EPRB⁸ correlations.

The easiest way we have found to explain the EPRB effect is to borrow from an idea of Paul O'Hara [31]. In that short easy-read paper O'Hara shows how Two-Slit interference can be reimagined as a result of isotropic spin-coupling together with entanglement of particles with the apertures of the slits.

Essentially, O'Hara claims that particles traversing the apertures must become entangled, for if not then there is no interference. The annoying crutch of his model is that it requires the detector to be sensitive to only one of the two spin polarizations. (We will come back to this soon.)

By the spin-statistics theorem [32] there exist only two rotationally invariant isotropically spin-correlated states,

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_+ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle) \\ \psi_- &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)\end{aligned}$$

both are entangled states, and ψ_- is referred to as the singlet (it's energy eigenvalues do not split). They are EPR correlated. O'Hara suggests this is the “primary cause of the interference phenomenon.”

⁸ These are distinct from EPR effects, which were more sweeping statements about the reality of measurable properties. EPRB is restricted to the Bell-Aspect type experiments.

FIG. 3: The detection event at P for some reason can only respond to one of ψ_+ or ψ_- , not both. However, the particle takes only one of the paths, green or pink, not both. Then there is interference.

We would object to such language, because, as any breathing statistician can tell you correlation is not causation. But we do not need to quibble about that just yet, since we have a deeper cause in mind. Thus we continue with O'Hara's train of thought (it's a gedankenexperiment mainly, but O'Hara adds later a way to test the proposal).

Now it gets slightly cryptic next in O'Hara's paper, so here we want to stipulate that we might be misreading it somehow, but it seems his proposal is that the detector is sensitive (somehow) to the state of spin polarization normal to the apertures. In such a way that only either the ψ_+ or the ψ_- state will get detected, the other will be absorbed without registering or transmitted. (Again, we will get back to this point soon.)

Taking this as given, then by conventional time evolution the initial pure state (say ψ_-) will evolve into

$$\psi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \psi_- + \rho \psi_+)$$

if the particle eventually is detected at detector angle $\phi = \alpha - \beta$ where here the amplitude $\rho = \rho(\phi)$, is computed by application of the rotation operators, as suggested in Figure 3. The result is the sensitive state, say ψ_+ , will only get detected with probability $\rho^2/2$ and the angular dependence ϕ then describes the Young interference pattern.

IV.B.1. Little deconstruction of O'Hara's model

We believe a crucial source of potential cognitive dissonance is in the use of the symbol ψ to describe the Two Slit system. In T4G theory this “ ψ ” is not a Dirac spinor. Or to deflate this claim, we suggest it is not to be thought of as a Dirac spinor. Maybe this is just obvious to most physicists, but it was not so obvious to us when we came to the literature, and was not something ever explicitly stated.

If one were to analyze the Two-Slit experiment using a Dirac spinor, or for photons a commuting spacetime

algebra Faraday bivector field, then it would be horridly complicated, one would use the path-integral formulation. While this can be done, it is far simpler to package the particle and the apertures up into an abstract “wavefunction”, we call ψ .

This should help defuse any anxiety about O’Hara’s model. The particle eventually detected can have been entangled with matter near the apertures. This is what the singlet states $|\psi_{\pm}\rangle$ are accounting for in stochastic transition amplitude terms. This ψ is thus *a little bit more than the single particle*. There is something near the apertures that it gets entangled with, or perhaps photons in the near-field of the apertures, or anything else. The issue is we do not know what this ‘else’ is, and so are forced to use an effective wavefunction description. The whole system then can possess an entanglement-like property (also known as *indivisibility* in the ISQM [9]) while we all nod knowingly to each other in on the secret that only single particles can ever be entangled.

The effective (abstract) wavefunction is only entangled by virtue of one (or more) of its constituent elementary particles being entangled. But such entanglement is powerful, it permits entire atoms and molecules to yield statistics exhibiting interference from non-Markov indivisible stochastic transitions, and hence appearances of being in superpositions.

IV.B.2. A test of O’Hara’s model

The test of this entanglement origins of interference O’Hara outlines is a modification of a design by Qureshi and Rahman [33] which proposes a transverse magnetic field to “wash out” the interference without needing coincidence counting in the Quantum Eraser experiment. To test O’Hara’s proposal the idea is to do the opposite.

If O’Hara’s model is valid then it should be possible to destroy the correlation using Stern-Gerlach magnets, without ever obtaining “which-way” information, so in O’Hara’s words [31]: “thereby demonstrating that it is not our knowledge of the situation that determines the final quantum state, but rather the way in which the states are correlated and transformed from coherent states into non-coherent states.”

Qureshi and Rahman would use the first magnet to obtain *which way* information as the particles enter the slit and then erase this information with another magnet after the particles exit the slits, to produce interference. This does not bother O’Hara’s model because the entanglement at the apertures is what causes the, let’s say, Ohara-interference.

O’Hara proposes the opposite, so that first the particles enter the slits undetected and form an interference pattern on the screen. Then a Stern-Gerlach magnet field, placed orthogonal to the screen and its normal, is turned on as the particles emerge from the slits. If O’Hara’s model is correct then the interference pattern will disappear by strategically positioning the magnet.

Whether or not O’Hara’s model can pass the test is irrelevant for our present purposes, because T4G has a slightly different account of interference due to entanglement, but it is a similar sort of concept to O’Hara’s.

IV.C. Is there another entangled way?

If we were only interested in the logical relations we would not need to write much more, because the fact T4G theory can be used to either derive or justify ISQM implies we already have a *statistical explanation* for all interference, it cannot occur without entanglement and if a measurement is sensitive to entanglement then there will be interference observable (if the appropriate data is collected) — completely generically, logically.

That is an ISQM result, and hence also a T4G result. (As Barandes has described it in seminars, it takes some getting used to indivisible non-Markov processes, “they’re just weird and counter-intuitive!”)

Physicists should not be content with stopping at stochastic laws as the final words. We are indeed not content with a statistical account, and as the final lead-in to the T4G account of EPRB results we will provide a more grounded spacetime description of what might be happening in O’Hara’s conception, though differing from O’Hara in that we do not need to evolve the states ψ_{\pm} in the prescribed way keeping the detector sensitivity to only one of the entangled states alive.

First, note that we are beyond EPRB. If the Two-Slit interference is explained by entanglement, then it is easy to simulate EPRB experiments. Almost embarrassingly easy. We will describe this first in very simple terms. Writing software to implement this is almost child’s play.

IV.D. Spinners, no Spinners!

We re-use Hedemann’s oscillators. This works for bosons or fermions, but we will get a bonus that it works in T4G for all ‘quantum’ particles.

Perhaps it is worth prefacing the model by pointing out the AdS–CFT duality between wormholes and entanglement is for black hole information loss analysis. But there is no obstacle to having the same duality in our de Sitter or FLRW spacetime, it is just not quite the same duality in the AdS–CFT dictionary sense, it is an exact equivalence. Our “boundary theory” is just the stuff on the T4G-cobordism boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 which we already know is a quantum theory, and does not need to presume conformal symmetry.

In words the model is as follows:

1. The Spinners (from Hedemann’s completely different, but related model) are oscillations along the wormhole ER-bridge of the Bell pair.
2. In T4G any particle or system that can form entangled states has wormhole topology of some kind

or algebraic variety.

3. When one fermion is measured by either Alice or Bob, this is violent on the Planck scale, the ER-bridge is broken. There is no wavefunction collapse since there is no wavefunction, but in the orthodox QM story the wavefunction here collapses.
4. Whether the 4-geon is entangled with matter near the apertures, or with vacuum should not matter too much, there should still be discernable interference until entanglement is destroyed by measurements that impose which-way information in the T4G cobordism.

This is consistent with GR, which has well-established topological censorship theorems [34–36]. Measuring the ‘hidden variable’ here, the ER-bridge state, would reveal topology, and so must collapse the wormhole, and that is what counts as a ‘measurement’, which Bob or Alice will observe. It is a real local variable, but topologically hidden from spacetime probes.

A particular model is hard to conjecture, because we have little to no empirical data on exactly what type of entanglement occurs in the Two-Slit experiment (on the presumption Nature is particulate, and not ‘waves and fields’). For this paper we can offer pseudocode for one simple simulation.

Algorithm 1: Simple T4G geon model for two-slit interference

```

 $\theta_{max} \leftarrow \arctan(W/2L)$ 
 $angles \leftarrow$  uniform array from 0 to  $\theta_{max}$  with  $n_{bins}$  points
 $intensities \leftarrow$  empty array
 $positions \leftarrow$  empty array
for each  $\theta$  in  $angles$  do
   $tally \leftarrow 0$ 
   $\Delta\phi \leftarrow \frac{2\pi d \sin(\theta)}{\lambda}$ 
   $P_{detect} \leftarrow \cos^2(\Delta\phi/4)$ 
  for  $i = 1$  to  $n_{geons}$  do
    if  $\text{random}() < P_{detect}$  then
       $tally \leftarrow tally + 1$ 
    end if
  end for
  append  $tally$  to  $intensities$ 
  append  $L \tan(\theta)$  to  $positions$ 
end for
return  $positions, intensities$ 

```

The loop could be expanded by a path propagator, but we can strip that away without too much loss of T4G particle verisimilitude, the result is just an idealized ray approximation (critique this as you please!).

Note that once you desire to strip down the T4G idea, you find it becomes completely banal. It is nothing more than a dopey way to Monte Carlo compute $\cos(\theta_{ab})$. The only T4G idea remaining is that we are supposing the

phase is physical oscillation across the wormhole mouths. All that we have done is promote the natural entanglement oscillations [37] to real geometry, in essence this is a very crude simple model of wormhole confined gravity waves. There is almost nothing else we can reasonably call them.

Also in this sense the model is as tautological or banal as Hedeman’s where he inserts $\cos(\theta_{ab})$ into his system of constraint equations. But T4G theory is more subtle. We do not need to insert the sinusoidal correlation “by hand” since we could instead harbour grand delusions of figuring out 4-geon topology and compute how the ER-bridges behave and oscillate, then we can fantasize about deducing they tend to obey sinusoids. But it takes little imagination to conjure up a wormhole oscillator model that has sinusoidal perturbations to first order. The trouble is testing it. Topology is censored, you see.

To simulate realistic effects like dispersion and washing-out of interference by entanglement collapse (real geometry collapse now, not mystical Copenhagen collapse) would be of some academic interest, though not essential for our present arguments.

IV.D.1. Wormhole Pinning

This is the phrase (*wormhole pinning*) we’ve settled on for the time being for these pure 4D spacetime single-particle interference models. O’Hara’s model could be reinterpreted as a pinning of one end of a wormhole, at matter near one aperture — rather than an assumption the detector is only sensitive to one spin polarization.

O’Hara is propagating amplitudes rather than real spacetime geometry oscillations, which is why he still uses the fiction of wavefunctions that live in Hilbert space, whereas we use only real spacetime geometry. But otherwise the models are near functorial equivalences up to instrumental practicalities, losing equivalence only under-the-hood in the particulars.

We believe, or conjecture, the effect should be more general if T4G is more than merely a good model, because there should be vacuum entanglement, and from the point of view of the detector screen it does not matter too much where in space the other end of the wormhole happens to be, what matters is that it has next to zero chance of hitting the detector (since that would then obviously wash-out the interference). That would mean in the above pseudocode we’d have to tally score the other end of the wormhole, both ends, so it gives a ballistic classical particle pattern.

We should just say that aperture pinning, which is closer to O’Hara’s model, seems a likely good first order candidate for taking a fixed end of the ER-bridge out of the game, as needed for interference (in this T4G model).

FIG. 4: Two-slit interference pattern produced by a 4-geon wormhole pinning model. Wormhole oscillations were made functions of the simulated geon path.

IV.D.2. Note on Variations

We’ve tried other variations of wormhole pinning, none of which so far reproduce the Young Interference pattern, though some appear like Fraunhofer patterns, so we might have a parameter issue to deal with.

For a paper ostensibly on EPRB, the only illustration we need to show is this deviant one, where a particular type of wormhole pinning simulation generates a Fraunhofer looking pattern Figure 4. What makes this result non-sinusoidal we believe, is that in this simulation we follow a 4-geon while rotating it’s wormhole phase. Only one end is going to be detected, but if the wormhole oscillation peak is nearer the other end it is a non-detect. The noiselessness of this simulation is due to the geon trajectory being a ray idealization.

With simpler indirect simulations where we essentially code in an explicit harmonic wormhole phase oscillation we can generate a perfect noiseless-case two-slit interference — a perfect sinusoid, and so not worth plotting.

The EPRB simulations likewise were indirect wormhole oscillation simulations, for which we code an explicit harmonic wormhole oscillation, and this yields (via the “dopey Monte Carlo”) a perfect Bell correlation function $E(a, b) = -\cos(a - b)$, and so again is not useful to plot.

The important point for this paper is that we get any interference pattern at all, not the form of the pattern which would obviously depend upon wormhole geometrodynamics details, which to-date are wholly unknown.

IV.E. EPRB Simulations

It is trivial to specialize from the Two-Slit simulation to the EPRB simulation. Although we do not know of an academic write-up, the physics cultural community is probably all aware of the Scott Aaronson Shetl Optimized blog where the challenge to “Bell Deniers” is the two classical computer test. You need to program two classical computers and get them emitting EPRB correlations some time later with no tricks up your sleeve.

Our case is the inverse, we are “Bell Affirmers” and the challenge is to have an absolutely minimal Third Charlie computer that simulates absolutely nothing but a Planck scale wormhole ER-bridge.

The minimal structure is a wormhole oscillation (reflected gravity wave). We are going to ignore the impedance matching and so forth for now, that’s too hard a problem to tackle for us. All we say is that a spin measurement with any decent magnets will destroy the ER-bridge, which in orthodox parlance is “collapse” of some wavefunction in a Hilbert space (fictions! ... from a T4G frame point⁹).

Three models are compared in the appendix §A in the form of pseudocode. The wormhole oscillations are modelled in the simplest way we thought possible in the pseudocode Algorithm-4.

Although it might take a skilled computer language linguist to see it, we hope the algorithmic similarity with our Two-Slit simulation for interference (Algorithm-1) is evident.

In EPRB experiments the T4G results are embarrassingly obvious. In T4G context entanglement is not mere statistical correlation, but is hard cold (nearly invisible) geometry, but also indivisible when accurately stochastically modelled. The difference in generic terms with Hedemann’s HV model is that,

- (a) T4G wormholes are not hidden, they’re just extraordinarily hard to probe without collapsing them [34]. (EPRB correlation experiments are such probes, they end in collapse.)
- (b) The EPRB correlations do not need coincidence counting in T4G, they should occur always.
- (c) The EPRB correlations should fade if the second lab measures their Bell pair at a very late time compared to Tsirelson bounds (converted to time delay).

We encourage you to have a go at writing a computer simulation for this. If you do things properly you will see it passes the Aaronson stringency tests, since you cannot possibly get the clock times in perfect sync if the frequencies of the wormhole oscillations are high enough to recover EPRB correlations, you do need a single wire at least connecting the two computers. (Of course, we do not have the budget to fly computers around so have not physically performed this test.) Trust us, it is non-classical! It is all *though the wormhole* not the Rabbit Hole.

It is going to be more fun to add noise and try to Monte Carlo simulate this, because then you could play around

⁹ We reiterate the plea to not read too much into our claims. You can believe in some reality to Hilbert space, it is just that in T4G theory we are denying ourselves that crutch, precisely for the bondage & discipline process of theory development.

with ideas about decoherence and whatnot, but we have not made such explorations.

It is far beyond our skill to go a level deeper and run geometrodynamics of spacetime simulations. If someone has such skill please put them in touch.

IV.E.1. Can wormhole pinning be tested?

If O’Hara’s model can be tested then we would consider it a test of our T4G wormhole pinning model for Two-Slits, and so by the arguments in this paper an indirect test of how EPRB correlations can be generated from Bell pairs¹⁰, without sacrificing any of our cherished principles except the one which T4G immediately abandons, namely (D). But note, we only abandon deterministic time evolution of 4-geons. If one prefers a mystical fields ontology then deterministic stochastic time-evolution remains as always. The stochastic variables can deterministically evolve. To our frame of mind though, a stochastic QM theory is not deterministic!

Other tests of this T4G wormhole pinning could be possible in EPRB context, since the pinning is with the Alice and Bob qubits themselves, the testable effect might be some engineered distortions of the wormholes. We have no concrete engineering proposals for how this could be arranged.

Another test is relational: if one can somehow manage EPRB counts without needing coincident counters then the T4G theory could be distinguished from Hedemann’s.

IV.F. How far does this generalize?

We are not aware of any EPR-like effects that cannot be accounted for with this T4G model. We do not even need spins. The T4G entanglement works for all measurements on the T4G-cobordism boundaries. This includes Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen’s original position and momentum complementarity.

On one boundary, say ∂M_1 we cannot record both position and momentum for a single particle, and in this case it does not just merely boil down to the gross old Heisenberg “disturbance” paradigm. In T4GT we can only admit equivalence classes of these 3-manifolds, and an experiment set-up to measure x cannot also measure p .

This is “just gravity” in one sense, and goes to show that gravity was always a quantum theory (of sorts, at least in the measurement proposition *logic*). It is not hard to motivate the additional postulates needed to derive QM from Quantum Logic in our case. In lieu of that, we’d prefer to mention something more for students

about why T4G Theory is non-classical, when all it seems to be is an extension of GR, but without resorting to the easy answer of, “We’ve got closed timelike curves.” The point to attempt to make is a little counterfactual history story, about how one might have realised GR was already a quantum theory before Quantum Theory.

The story *could have been* that once people overcame a fear of black holes, then the collapse of matter into a black hole would be the limit on measurements. Then these general relativists should have been able to discover Plank’s constant this way, through the black hole thermodynamics. It’s nice or “fun to imagine” this could have been the way Twentieth Century physics could have evolved. The question is, can that be done without using QFT?

We believe not — or not without some kind of *particle postulate* like the topological 4-geon. There does need to be some quantum axiom we suspect. That’s the final interim answer for our students: classical mechanics has back holes, so does have topological censorship, but classical mechanics does not exploit the possibility elementary particles are spacetime topology. Topology is discrete, hence “quantum” in a very raw primitive sense, so presuming *elementary* particles are spacetime topology is a quantum postulate. It is hard to see how black hole thermodynamics could have been discovered without some such postulate (the alternative to topology would be quantum fields, which can have non-local correlators and thus permit Hawking radiation).

For sharper students, this links back to the T4G-cobordism boundary — which is where T4G quantum mechanics is *defined* — they may ask, *why does the algebra of observables obey Heisenberg Uncertainty relations on the boundaries?* The answer is in the Spacetime Algebra [39], which although normal pseudo-euclidean geometry it is a Clifford algebra, and so has fundamental non-commuting generators for the Lie algebra (all the Lie groups are spin groups [40], and have bivector or similar generators, and these are elements of regular spacetime geometry). If you do not presuppose spacetime is real then you do not have available the same commutation relations, you’d be putting them in by hand or trying to “emerge” them from some other bedrock.

This is getting beyond the scope of this paper, but the even keener students should then ask why, or how, $\hbar = 1$ in the Spacetime Algebra commutation relations can get promoted to something physically important in so much quantum theory, from single photons, to black hole horizons? Well, good question! Go answer it for homework. But, you know, maybe our cosmos is a 4D spacetime afterall? Maybe the universe tells us things in plain light that we are too arrogant to want to believe because...?¹¹

¹⁰ O’Hara has made a similar link between Two-Slit results and EPRB [38].

¹¹ You are too elite and are above all that simplistic 4D stuff! To which we would reply *please then solve the geometrization prob-*

The cost of leaning on O’Hara’s more particular model is that we are currently unable to force a good distinction, but that is why we mentioned the Qureshi–Rahman test, since if perchance O’Hara’s model fails, it would not mean doom for local causal particle physics, since T4G could still pass that particular test.

To our knowledge T4G would be in agreement with any orthodox QM tests associated with probing *interference as always a result of entanglement*. The subtlety is that entanglement is ubiquitous, and the vacuum (in at least the theory of QFT) is highly entangled, and so probing the very fine structure of interference effects might not be the best way to test T4G theory.

This is just our guess but it seems more likely good tests will come in gravity wave detection and the recent activity in testing gravity Two-Slit experiments; or so-called *spin-witnesses of quantum gravity* [41]. There is also the avenue of EPR without coincidence counters, which would help separate T4G from Hedemann’s model.

* * *

If we were to sum up then, the Maldacena–Susskind koan is the briefest way, but we would add a directional embellishment:

$$\boxed{\text{ER} \Rightarrow \text{EPR}}$$

because we cannot get ER-bridges just from mystical EPR correlation, since that’s a multiple-realization problem.

There have been other advances in building upon the original ER=EPR Conjecture, but we will not review them here. One to mention is a holographic duality result that an EPR Pair has a wormhole [42]. In this result from Jensen and Karch they get classically non-traversable wormholes, which is consistent with T4G, since we would invoke Friedman’s topological censorship [34], and not require holography.

There is also scope, we believe, for finding the Standard Model within T4G theory, and evidence in that direction is given by two other spacetime accounts for the Standard Model [43, 44] (Lasenby) and [45] (Lisi), but also see [44, 46] (Hestenes). This will be a subject we hope for a later T4G preprint [24].

Potential no-go theorems comparing theory with experiment, where experiment enforces some no-go, have not been a focus of our efforts to date, so we would like to caution against anyone miss-reading us who claims T4G is a fully fledged quantum gravity theory.

The next few sections before our conclusions are some additional remarks inspired by all we have discussed so far, meant to spark further research interests.

IV.G. Can we say interference is ubiquitous?

We’ve pointed out all interference is a result of entanglement, however this applies only to *single particles*. All collective particle wave phenomena are “emergent” — for want of a better word — and not intrinsically *quantum*.

In this light, all EPR experiments are really interference effects. Or one could view things semantically the other way around: all interference of single particles is the effect of entanglement.

This is an uncommon view, not easy to find in previous literature. We would say interference is ubiquitous, but routinely we completely lack measurement records ourselves which reveal all the interference. This is in alignment with ISQM, which *as a point of logic* would say the same thing. Everywhere there is entanglement we should see interference, but our experiments are never set up to record all the data to re-compile to visualize the interference. Not to mention, the generic experiment (say scattering at CERN) loses so much information it would be debatable whether it is ever humanly possible to reconstruct all the interference. Imagine how many detectors we’d need.

IV.H. Time ordering

Another way to view the T4G resolution of the “EPR Paradox” from old Einstein’s vantage, would be to adjust how you consider our measurement laboratories situated in time. We mention this because if one (dopily) takes EPR as the only Rosetta Stone for deciphering quantum gravity then surely there are other models that use the same type of resolution. We consider superdeterminism to be just one such adjustment. We think it’s the dopey one, but not to be ruled out. The Transactional Interpretation is another, Price and Wharton’s retrocausality yet another. Less elegant all than T4G in our present opinion.

However, one can still harbour a soft spot for views that adjust our understanding of time, and that give much less weight to human perceived psychological time than the more objective concepts of physical time. When psychological prejudices get demolished that’s normally a very good thing for civilization.

Recall the quote from the Hofer-Szabó paper on common cause completeability on page 5.

The T4G account of EPR is rather nice in that for measurement instrument bits and pieces we certainly do have events that are not *directly causally related* between Alice and Bob once they are spacelike separated. Furthermore, T4G does not force us to posit an *ad hoc* merological or mystical relation between the detection events. Yet we have a nice simple *completed* common cause, since in T4G theory entanglement is geometry.

The measurement set-ups at Alice and Bob are of fundamental importance in T4G theory, precisely because at T4G-cobordism boundaries we cannot have simultaneous

lem for 4D manifolds. Should be “basic” for you 11 dimensional brained elites, huh?

measurement of incommensurate observables. The T4G angle is that this is a consequence of GR or ‘gravity’ meaning gravity writ large, not merely Einstein’s Equations.

If you have already concluded T4G theory is wrong for some reason, let us insist that there might be other generalizations of a similar concept. The generic concept is:

Entanglement is geometric.

In geometric algebra the bipartite structure of the entanglement is almost always ‘algebraicized’ too early on, before the real geometry is discussed, for instance, the use of complex Clifford algebra in the thesis of [47]. Yet Imahori recognizes to some extent that the EPR Paradox has been partially geometrized, and this is consistent with our T4G picture which is fully geometrized. To describe our T4G model algebraically one must impose some bipartite or “complex” or tensor product structure. Another discussion supporting this conjecture is [48].

If you can find another account for entanglement that is geometric or the algebra at least can be geometrized, then you might have discovered a whole new class of quantum gravity theories. You might even find this concept in String Theory? May that provide a small clue about what alligator in the Swamp land you are walking atop of?

IV.I. A remark on determinism

It might also be helpful to compare the T4G theory resolution with Bell’s 1981 paper [49]. There Bell points out if Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen (hence also ourselves) wish to have a model that retains all the cherished Principles, (SI, L, LC, D, RCC) then there must be some real properties fixed *in advance of observation*, that are not contained in the quantum formalism, hence , “...that formalism for EPR is incomplete.”

Those are well chosen words. We do have such a model, and yep, check, it does claim quantum mechanics is incomplete.

However, Determinism (D) is a might murky. What we think T4G might settle upon (should it pass tests and gain some validity or credence) is that determinism is a bit of a meaningless concept, as is superdeterminism, as remarked earlier in our introduction. In T4G Theory something is always determining things, but in a generic finite time spacetime cobordism region there is no perfect Cauchy development, and physics in the T4G model remains irreducibly probabilistic for entities like human beings. We can imagine the 4D Block Universe, but it is of no use to us here and now, except for philosophical talk.

If you think about it carefully you can also squeeze T4G theory to match Ellis’ *Crystallizing Block Universe* conception [50], though that is not how we would think

of spacetime. It has been however in times of idle contemplation how we sometimes think of spacetime. It is a useful concept to think about.

IV.J. Options when model-building

Sprawling programs like String Theory have come in for some criticism in recent years. A lot of it is misdirected we think, because in theoretical physics, as in all sciences, we have little option but to model-build. It is ok if some stick to pure experimental and phenomenological work too, in an instrumentalist mode, cataloguing and ‘data refining,’ but there’s no one right way to go about science.

Now here we urge physicists to wake up a tad and not ignore the next two paragraphs!

The author’s other expertise is macroeconomics. The relevance here is that there is no essential monetary problem in science like String Theory “grabbing all the funds,” or the big collider experiments. Science funding takes such a small slice of the public investment pie that it is laughable to have any moral qualms about some of the big budgets, even the Superconducting Supercollider. The SSC would have been a tiny fraction of US GDP, and hardly worth writing to the US Treasury about (who can always drop a trillion dollar platinum coin in their box at the FED). In an MMT system [51, 52] (which is all nations on the earth today) there is never any problem *finding the money*. Governments create their tax credits with computer account entries [53]. The real issue is how many and what type of *real resources* will the government’s spending consume that now will no longer be available for hire in the private sector?

For a monopoly currency issuer the ‘dollar cost’ is completely irrelevant. Government spending has never *caused* a hyperinflation event in all recorded history (this is direct research from a very right-wing think tank [54]). The cause is always something else, usually a supply shock¹², and a rise in government net spending is a consequence, not the cause. A necessary consequence otherwise people start dying on the street. Thus physicists need to stop worrying about the monetary costs — to governments (not so for private research houses) — of their research — because none of it is “tax payer funded,” it’s the other way around, all government net spending (aka. “the deficit”) is providing the tax credits *to* the tax payers with which they can (in the macro) extinguish their tax liabilities. By accounting identity the “government debt” is penny-for-penny the net non-government

¹² Like war, war reparations, famine, pestilence (goodness, when has that ever happened recently?), corruption, &c. “Sarcasm has no place in a scientific article,” we hear the gatekeepers crying. Not sure about you, but I am a human who feels things, not a meat machine, and Science has been an enormous shaper of social conditions, for good and for bad.

sector *savings* (of government scorepoints, aka. ‘dollars’). A rather good record of account if it rises with a growing population, a rather horrific thing if it declines *without prices also declining*, and the reality is prices hardly ever decline, they just go to zero when a product is no longer for sale.

So science talking heads who fear-monger about inflation and the government debt literally have it all backwards. Saner scientists should think harder — when advocating for public science — more about the real resource costs. People are easy to employ, most scientists do not mind working in the public sector, and so can always be fully employed [55]. No starving postdocs or job precarity need exist. For heavens sake geeks, wake up! Start thinking in terms of science employment solidarity. It’s not a raw competition, backwards government policy artificially creates the nasty competition.

May we now say, how about some government research funds for T4G theory? Pencil and paper and some computers will do for a start. When our postdocs buy the coffee and pencils and computer chair cushions, it will be literally funding tax payers.

The T4G framework is just one more way to model many quantum gravity phenomena. Before summing things up, it is worth comparing a more ontological model like T4G with more logical based models like ISQM, or the Leifer–Spekkens Bayesian system. Rather than direct comparison (which would presume familiarity with the latter model which we do not have) we would like to make just a short general remark on the physical principles (SI, RCC, R, L, LC) most EPRB discussion revolves around.

The T4G framework is consistent with Barandes’ concept of *causal locality* but without sacrificing (RCC) and without caring about Determinism (D) [you may have (D) or not have (D), depending on your definitions], because *through the wormhole* no signal ever propagates faster than light. However, from the *Minkowski Lens*, where the ER-bridge is “invisible” then the principle among our principles we appear to abandon is (L). But you could also argue for retaining (L) and abandoning (LC) since without a wormhole-like model of what *causes* the EPRB correlations one is really at a loss to claim precisely which principle is getting abandoned. One can put a foot in either of Wiseman’s Camps. This highlights the futility of *starting* from some “camp” or some imposed ideology. Principles are good, but if one has a mutually exclusive choice then choice is merely ‘ok’ provided one does not get ideological about it.

Lacking a firm foundation we should start from one choice and see where it leads, but then return and try the others. Science is not a system of exploration that treats one-way ventures well. Fortunately public sector science does not need to worry about *finding the money* if we took a wrong turn to a failed venture and need to redirect funding to the other road. All we lose is time. This need not cause catastrophic climate warming or the opposite Snowball Earth. Nor is it a moral hazard *pro-*

vided we achieved some semblance of a democracy, because then government does not need market forces to dictate research directions, the public needs and opinions can be the weights, and, regardless, governments can always ensure full employment of geeks.

V. CONCLUSIONS

It is very depressing to end a summary section on, “more work needs to be done,” so we can get that out of the way early: T4G theory is so immature that it is embarrassing to write about it even for preprint amusement. Having noted that, it is a darn fun theory to play with, and if some geometrodynamics no-go result destroys the whole project that’d be even sadder than finishing this paper at this full stop.

After some review and digressions we have implicitly argued in this paper — in a round-about way — that a significant prejudice in theoretical physics against violation of special relativity (SR) has led to a form of groupthink which blocks an obvious resolution to the tension between EPRB experiments and the principles we would like to retain in our models of physical reality: (SI), (L), (LC), (R) and (RCC).

This groupthink is only a social behaviour we are meek to elaborate upon, having no sociology credentials, and we name the social phenomena in the physics community such only for lack of a deeper analysis. Perhaps there is just a temporary theory road blindness, or perhaps the groupthink is totally correct and our topological 4-geon alternative wrong and all similar approaches to a resolution are wrong? — these would include the Transactional Interpretation, retrocausal signalling and the like, which also violate special relativity.

One justification for claiming there is mild groupthink is that GR already violates SR. While this is not controversial, because the way GR violates SR is considered tame, the blindness to deeper violation is commonly overlooked. For not only may GR permit curved spacetime, it may permit non-trivial local topology, including stable wormholes on about the Planck scale, where violation of weak energy conditions can persist [56, 57]. This should not be controversial, given that almost every second proposal for quantum gravity considers some variety of *foamy spacetime*.

Related to these issues is what exactly is happening at the breakdown of semi-classical ‘quantum gravity’ and what that even means [58]? What it means for our present purposes is that theoreticians should not too glibly dismiss Planck scale wormholes. Visser [59] has even pointed out gravitational vacuum polarization violates *all* the classical energy conditions, and that is just in standard QFT.

A more particularly interesting result of Visser’s is that scale anomaly violation implies violation of the average null energy condition (ANEC) [60]. Energy condition violations are necessary for existence of stable wormholes.

Visser’s results altogether strongly imply Planck scale wormholes may exist and could be traversable (in some sense, at least qubit level information) meaning that the standard constraints preventing traversable wormholes are lifted at the quantum level. This occurs in the mathematical models because the trace anomaly adds negative energy contributions to the stress-energy tensor along null geodesics.

We may also link this to leptogenesis and baryogenesis. At the CPT-symmetric early universe [61] exact scale invariance applies due to the ultrahigh temperatures (massless radiation domination), but this gets ‘spontaneously broken’ as the universe cools. An extremely curious wild speculation springs to mind: supposing the conformally symmetric radiation dominated extreme early universe does not generate scale anomalies, and (for some reason, energy conditions perhaps) does not permit traversable wormholes? Then the very early universe might do the exact opposite to Visser, namely not lift WEC/ANEC, and may conversely suppress quantum gravity effects, in principle — in the T4G picture — suppressing quantum mechanics, at least on average (because, one can argue, when would a thermal symmetry suppression ever be exact?). It is a distinct possibility because on the assumption T4G is correct about some things minimalistically, then we *need* wormholes to be traversable in some manner for *any* quantum mechanics whatsoever.

One can be hypercritical and say this *is* a violation of GR, but we think this is hyperbole. If by “GR” one means Einstein’s Equations then yes, the proposal in this paper violates “GR” and is all the *better* for it. Our proposal is still a spacetime theory of gravity grounded in spacetime algebra and symmetry principles. It is also radically minimalist, if that is of appeal to theoreticians (it should be).

The obvious things to do when faced with theory obstacles or no-go results (like EPRB) is to relax something; or introduce new constructs. The more parsimonious approach is to first consider relaxing conditions. Admitting Planck scale wormhole topology as an explicit account for entanglement is too parsimonious to overlook. This is hence what we propose: topological 4-geon theory (T4G) and a purely 4D spacetime foundation for quantum theory. If the reader is pleased to do so then introducing wormhole topology could be regarded instead as a new construct. Either way, that’s just semantics, and the evident parsimony of the proposal still stands.

The T4G resolution of EPRB is fairly unique (among known alternatives) in not requiring abandonment of any of the principles (SI), (L), (LC), (R) and (RCC). The summary explanation is that all entanglement is *through the wormhole*.

The one other cherished principle you might desire is determinism (D), but honestly this is not one we cherish. Something ultimately determines things, but our comment on (D) is just that we have no need to clutch at the straws of Many Worlds, and that is a very good thing, since there are too many straws to even find one to grab

in that basket of multiversal madness.

Measurement setting independence holds because the EPR correlations are through the wormhole. Likewise (L) and (LC) hold provided Minkowski topology is not imposed. *Through the wormhole* Minkowski topology is mangled, but we still have connected 4D spacetime and Lorentzian structure. (R) holds trivially since all the stochastic dynamics and contextuality in T4G is due to spacetime cobordism indivisibility and the cobordism boundary measurement logic of propositions, not anti-realism. (RCC) still holds because no Bell Pairs have ever been manufactured or observed that did not originate in a lightcone causal consistent process, like a pair production event, or parametric down-conversion; together with the later measurement correlations after spacelike separation being due to *one-way* signalling through the wormhole.

The *one-way signalling* does not violate SR in any reference frame because the Minkowski reference frame is not a rigid GR concept here even with both Alice and Bob laboratories inertial and at relative rest: either Alice’s side or Bob’s side collapses the ER-bridge, but SR tells us not to worry about the notion of “who went first” since that is frame dependent, so not an absolute physical question. Alice and Bob can compare clocks later and agree who got the signal ‘first’ if that ever matters. They will not know until they can share classical SR non-violating information.

Modifying (RCC) — Reichenbach’s common cause principle — did appeal, and was an option entertained by Barandes, whom we have closely followed. To summarize the T4G view of (RCC) we can recall the Spekkens and Wood [14] note we indirectly quoted on page 6. This is the note that any model that retains (RCC) must involve ‘fine tuning’ that any such model must hide some causal channel from “agents in the world” — either Alice or Bob or their supervisor Zeilinger. Well, indeed! Who can say they’ve ever seen a T4G wormhole? The more serious point is we think Spekkens and Wood have too narrowly framed the (RCC) issue. If they take special relativity as sacrosanct then that’s too rigid an ideology, we are in the quantum gravity regime when doing EPR experiments — at least according to T4G and some folks at Google and Caltech [62] and Lenny Susskind [63, 64]. So any theorizing that casts doubt on (RCC) but has presumed (SR) to hold is *possibly* invalid from our point of few (and Google–Caltech).

There is one point which T4G theory abandons, but it is not a principle, namely we would agree with Einstein and Schrödinger that quantum mechanics was incomplete. But so was classical mechanics and *classical* GR. Hardly revolutionary ideas *today* to worry about abandoning.

Appendix A: Pseudocode for EPRB simulations

We’ve chosen to demonstrate pseudocode that is easy to write in a high level language like Python or Julia, and

that which also is not compute intensive. We imagine any T4G model proper would be a geometrodynamics simulation and consume vast compute resources (as far as we can envisage). But we do not see that level of rigour to be necessary to communicate the basic ideas in this paper.

Algorithm-2 is like our control. In your implementation you should get the classical mechanics triangular correlation function.

Note this does not conflict with Hedemann [16] who has a local hidden variable model, but which has distinctly non-classical features — upon one reading — or has the imposition of coincidence counting with classical-like HV upon another reading. In Hedemann’s case the Bell Inequality cannot even be derived.

Algorithm 2: Classical Bell EPR Model

```

 $\theta_{angles} \leftarrow$  uniform array from 0 to  $2\pi$  with 100 points
Initialize result arrays:  $AB[100][100]$ ,  $A[100]$ ,  $B[100]$ 
function GENERATELAMBDA
  return uniform random array from 0 to  $2\pi$  with  $N$ 
  elements
end function
function MEASUREMENTA( $a, \lambda$ )
  return  $\text{sign}(\cos(a - \lambda))$ 
end function
function MEASUREMENTB( $b, \lambda$ )
  return  $-\text{MeasurementA}(b, \lambda)$ 
end function
function RUNCLASSICAL
   $\lambda \leftarrow \text{GenerateLambda}()$ 
  for  $i = 0$  to 99 do
     $a \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[i]$ 
     $A_{results} \leftarrow \text{MeasurementA}(a, \lambda)$ 
     $A[i] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results})$ 
    for  $j = 0$  to 99 do
       $b \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[j]$ 
       $B_{results} \leftarrow \text{MeasurementB}(b, \lambda)$ 
       $AB[i][j] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results} \times B_{results})$ 
    end for
     $B[i] \leftarrow \text{mean}(B_{results})$ 
  end for
end function

# Common to All Models
function COMPUTEBELLINEQUALITY
   $P_{ab} \leftarrow AB[0][:]$   $\triangleright$  Correlations for  $a = 0$ 
   $P_{ac} \leftarrow AB[0][:]$ 
   $LHS \leftarrow |P_{ab} - P_{ac}|$   $\triangleright$  Element-wise for all angle
  pairs
   $RHS \leftarrow 1 + AB$   $\triangleright$  All pairwise correlations
   $\Delta \leftarrow LHS - RHS$ 
  return  $\Delta$ 
end function

```

Checking the QM Code

Algorithm-3 is a direct algorithm for spitting out

the expected QM correlation for EPRB, $E(A, B) = -\cos(\theta_{ab})$.

Algorithm 3: Quantum Bell EPR Model

```

function RUNQUANTUM
  for  $i = 0$  to 99 do
     $a \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[i]$ 
    for  $j = 0$  to 99 do
       $b \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[j]$ 
       $p_{same} \leftarrow (1 - \cos(a - b))/2$ 
       $same \leftarrow$  array of  $N$  random bools with prob-
      ability  $p_{same}$ 
       $outcomes \leftarrow$  array of  $N$  random choices
      from  $\{-1, +1\}$ 
       $A_{results} \leftarrow outcomes$ 
       $B_{results} \leftarrow$  where  $same$  is true:  $outcomes$ ,
      else:  $-outcomes$ 
       $AB[i][j] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results} \times B_{results})$ 
    if  $i = 0$  then
       $A[j] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results})$ 
       $B[j] \leftarrow \text{mean}(B_{results})$ 
    end if
  end for
end function

```

Simple version of the wormhole EPR model

Algorithm-4 is a quasi-simulation of oscillations through the wormhole which should numerically replicate the output of Algorithm-3.

Algorithm 4: Wormhole Bell EPR Model

```

function GENERATELAMBDAWORMHOLE
   $\theta_0 \leftarrow$  uniform random from 0 to  $2\pi$ 
   $\lambda \leftarrow$  uniform random array from 0 to  $2\pi$  with  $N$ 
  elements
  return  $\lambda$ 
end function
function MEASUREMENTAWORMHOLE( $a, \lambda$ )
  return  $\text{sign}(\cos(\lambda - a))$ 
end function
function MEASUREMENTBFROMA( $b, a, \lambda$ )
  return  $\text{sign}(\cos(\lambda - a)) \times \cos(a - b + \pi)$ 
end function
function RUNWORMHOLE
  for  $i = 0$  to 99 do
     $a \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[i]$ 
    for  $j = 0$  to 99 do
       $b \leftarrow \theta_{angles}[j]$ 
       $\lambda \leftarrow \text{GenerateLambdaWormhole}()$ 
       $A_{results} \leftarrow \text{MeasurementAWormhole}(a, \lambda)$ 
       $B_{results} \leftarrow \text{MeasurementBFromA}(b, a, \lambda)$ 
       $AB[i][j] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results} \times B_{results})$ 
    end for
     $A[i] \leftarrow \text{mean}(A_{results})$ 
     $B[i] \leftarrow \text{mean}(B_{results})$ 
  end for

```

end for

end function

-
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